

HISTORY OF CONSTRUCTION OF RESERVOIRS WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF AGRICULTURAL POLICY OF THE SOVIET STATE IN THE KASHKADARYA OASIS

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the history of the construction of the water reservoir during the years of Soviet power in the Kashkadarya oasis, as well as the development of new lands and the history of the irrigation system, based on archival and primary sources. The scope, results and consequences of the work done during the construction of water reservoirs are covered with historical evidence.

During the years of Soviet power, serious attention was paid to the development of the irrigation system in the republic, as a result of which many reservoirs were built. These creative works, in turn, made it possible to collect and preserve water supplies for irrigation. However, their excessive construction was closely related to the then cotton monopoly policy of the center, and the irrigation sector was aimed at developing cotton growing. The natural conditions and capabilities of the republic were almost not taken into account during the construction of water bodies. For this reason, the excessive construction of waterworks has naturally caused environmental problems. However, the Soviet authorities did not pay attention to such problems. They were only interested in growing cotton and obtaining a higher yield, as well as transporting the finished raw material to the center.

It is known that in areas where natural water sources are insufficient, water facilities are built in order to supply the land with water. Kashkadarya region is a region located on the southern borders of Uzbekistan, and the existence of a favorable geographical environment, fertile land, and large areas provide the opportunity to grow fertile agricultural products here. But at the same time, the only problem in the oasis is the lack of natural water sources. To date, we have been able to grow agricultural products in the country only through the use of existing water facilities and the use of modern technologies in providing water to the land.

Reservoirs are the most important water source for the country's water supply. Reservoirs are artificial lakes created by man in the bed of a river or stream, in a depression or depression on the surface of the earth through dams and various barriers. Reservoirs are built with the aim of distributing river flows over the seasons and controlling floods in accordance

with the water needs of industry, agriculture, the local population, transport and other sectors of the economy.¹

The biggest works of these years were carried out in water management. Large water reservoirs were built in the Kashkadarya oasis in order to meet the water needs of areas with a shortage of water during the development of the Karshi desert. In particular, on October 21, 1960, the decision of the Council of Ministers of Uzbekistan "On the construction of the Pachkamar reservoir" was adopted.² The Ministry of Land Reclamation and Water Management of the Uzbek SSR instructed the Uzgirovodkhoz Institute to develop this project - the construction of a reservoir. Chief Engineer K.K. The project, worth 14,349.05 thousand rubles, drawn up by Pisarchik, was approved on November 3, 1961.³ Before the construction of the facility, only 20 thousand hectares of the 55 thousand hectares of land available in the Guzor region were irrigated. ⁴

The policy on the construction of reservoirs was not relaxed at all, but became stricter every year. In particular, thanks to the construction of irrigation in the region in 1971-1990, the number of operating reservoirs in the region reached 13. The construction of 3 reservoirs continued, and design work for the 1st reservoir was completed. From all the above information, it is known that the goal of the Soviet government in constructing reservoirs in the oasis was to establish regular irrigation of irrigated lands and improve cotton production. Accumulating water resources for continuous irrigation of large cotton fields was considered a very important issue for the Soviets. However, in a number of cases, the above irrigation construction measures were not fully implemented. The reason for this was that during the construction of many irrigation structures, local conditions and the ecological situation of the republic were not taken into account, while at the same time other tasks were determined from the center and their implementation was made a condition before the only facility was completely built.

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